

CONCEPTUAL FEATURES OF OXYMORON IN LITERARY WORKS

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Abstract. *The article deals with conceptuality in where oxymoron as one of the stylistic devices in the literature. As the basic requirement in understanding an expression of oxymoron in which shows the productive in the language through the principles of transformational grammar. On the other hand, in learning or analyzing language, people should consider literature as a way of how language and stylistic construction are used. In this article will show how psycholinguistic investigation suggests that literal texts such as novel, poet, story are processed differently than literal speech, while relatively conventionalized and contextually salient oxymoron is processed more like literal speech. This conceptuality in the view of “cognitive linguists” like George Lakoff that all or nearly all thought is essentially oxymoronically. There are currently a few main conceptuality of oxymoron: juxtaposition, category-transfer, feature-matching, and structural alignment. Structural alignment deals best with the widest range of examples; but it still fails to account for the complexity and richness of fairly novel, poetic oxymoron.*

Key words: *formation of oxymoron in literary texts, an interpretation of conceptuality, the cognitive approach of oxymoron, analyzing process under psycho-cognitive principles.*

Introduction: Nearly not any statements have been made on how the oxymoron is reacted to the readers either reading any sentences belonged to oxymoron or communicating.

Actually, there are many dictionaries and handbooks only point out the contradictory or incongruous combination of this poetic use of words, however they do not indicate how the constituents combine the concrete meaning of it, in other words can not identify the clear of concept in the context. Naturally, there will be a question why it has not been made any exact interpretation of this two contradicting word – combination yet, still continuing the main object to discover a suitable frame for it in contextual texts. But I have tried to provide some information on oxymoron in variety process how to identify its basic meaning is interpreted to the readers. Firstly, should we identify the oxymoron with lexical stylistic device, how they connected to each other? Secondly, what is the aim of “concept” term connecting with this part?

Lexical stylistic – devices have specific meaning in contextual texts which illustrate a certain type of communication in speech. One of them is an oxymoron including its semantics and cognition qualities are used as a main role in the literary texts which abounding with odd peculiarities in sentences. It is known that the term – oxymoron is one of the style devices that involves in stylistics as being a branch of linguistics that plays the various functional styles of speech. *Oxymoron* is one type of absurdity which entails irreconcilable elements of meaning or reference (Leech, 1968, :138). Oxymoron is literary figures of speech usually composed of a pair of neighboring contradictory words (often with a sentence). So each reader should be careful of getting acquaintance of different styles, basically about using oxymoron in the literature and provide them with necessary materials to illustrate information. First, there have been a little awareness of stylistic devices, their functions, expressive means in the stylistics as

well stylistic devices which are distinguished into many parts according to its aspects. Stylistic devices calling figures of speech make use of a figurative meaning of the language elements and thus form a vivid image. It is clear that the oxymoron word in literary contexts may acquire additional lexical meanings not fixed in dictionaries, what we have named contextual meanings.

To depict it as contradicting agreement between two word of speech and they intensify the meaning in context. Like these agreements in sentences mainly depend on various functional features which is attracted the society to understand deeply what is going in contextual in a group of words. Approaching by an oxymoron device is used in literary textbooks to exaggerate the sense of contents and this process may be unusual situation for the first reader. Taking into all meaningful states, it can create some experiencing conscious for them. Adding to it, oxymoron is separated differently from others under treating extraordinary way as well as its functions by linguistic studies certain categories. Following trails through studying oxymoron reveals some interesting clipped examples its precise techniques in this research paper and can be used as manual note for each readers.

Now we look widely about the “concept” term with oxymoron that is abstract ideas or general notions that occur in the mind, in speech and in thought. Being fundamental building blocks of thoughts and beliefs which play an important role in all aspects of cognition. So, it is clear that concept and oxymoron both connected in an interpretation in this article under linguistics, psychology, philosophy and is also interested in the logical and psychological structure of concepts, and how they are put together to form of thoughts and sentences. It is served as basic tendency on using interdisciplinary approach called cognitive science.

Broadening this conceptuality on the combination of two contradictory/opposites in a single sentence, the conceptuality of oxymoron is an entire phrase/ contradictory meaningful word combination but, upon further investigation, could be true or plausible interpretation in the literary context. Another approach of conceptuality of oxymoron to develop its linguistic and cognition process in literary texts with lexical – semantic, lexicon, grammar, phonology. The object of lexical – cognitive characters of an oxymoron device invokes versatile expressive points with various odd concepts in connecting word sentences in literary contexts which emphasis effect and peculiarities in fiction plays as well as increase the phenomenal character, events and acts. Due to it, it is formed unordinary blooming character involving new information. However, what are principles to be basis its new born sentence structures? Can people catch easily its contradicting polysemous process in using literary texts?

The origin the word of oxymoron (Greek oxys + moros-“pointedly foolish”) is a stylistic device the syntactic and semantic structures of which come to clashes. It involves a combination of two contrasting ideas within the same syntactical whole, thus referring some feature to an object incompatible with it. As a rule, one of the two members of oxymoron illuminates the feature which is universally observed and acknowledged while the other one offers a purely subjective individual perception of the object. Kukharenko names three structural patterns that are possible to build lexical word combination through stylistic process which is mentioned in the text- book Stylistics by Galperin.

Most researchers (such as Academician V.V.Vinogradov.) have learnt about language forms of the object of stylistics, synonyms of lexical – grammar, although it is considered as examining the meaning of language patterns, it can be taken into consideration its classification, means of lingua – stylistic and its colored emotional – expressive ways by distinguishing.

To develop the article, firstly that demonstrated the origin of word combinations *lingua – cognitive* means to understanding the language patterns by coordinating it with using characters of oxymoron basically literary prose. *Lingua – cognitive* or cognitive linguistic concept began in the late 1970s in response to the dominant, generative paradigm in linguistics. Unlike the work in generative linguistics, defined by the Chomskyan revolution, cognitive linguists assume the analysis of the conceptual and experiential basis of linguistic categories and constructs is of primary importance: the formal structures of language are studied not as if they were autonomous, but as reflections of general conceptual organization, categorization principles, and processing mechanisms. [Gibbs, 1994:Lakoff,1990]

Thus, it may another question about coming the term oxymoron. It causes to join word sentences through contradicting sympathy under conflict manner and formulate new ideas than expected situation. Understanding its using in contexts might be a little vague about how to make use of a figurative meaning of the language elements whereas to create a vivid image by communicating each other. Else, the stylistic device and its functional factors according to its treating in various aspects are surveyed and gave his explanations by uzbek scientists A. Sulaymonov “ About styles of language” , academician G'.Abdurahmonov. Naturally, to explore oxymoron in the literary texts demands an excessive trying to analyze each individual person plus make authorities to combust allegorical stories, poems and plays. All of them are based on polysemantic effect which is created controversial questions in problematic situations and the whole process discovers as a lexicology and certain stylistic purposes. Therefore, most of them including lingu-cognitive qualities have been determined all literary texts in a researching paper by providing proof of necessary details and examining examples to manifest and interplay between the primary and one of the derivative meaning we are again with a stylistic device.

An oxymoron combines two seemingly contradictory or opposite ideas to create rhetorical or poetic effect and reveal a deeper truth. Generally, the ideas will come as two separate words placed side by side. The most common type of oxymoron is an adjective followed by a noun, adverb and verb that build two contradicting word patterns in the readings although they could not fit with each other. Oxymorons are often used in everyday conversation and in a breadth of writing, such as literature, poetry, and songwriting.

One oxymoron example is “ *How cheerfully he seems to grin,
how neatly spreads his claws,
And welcome little fishes in,
With gently smiling jaws* ”

An analysis of these amalgamations (rhyme from Lewis Carroll “ Alice’s Adventures in Wonderland ” p.27) which describes appearance with incooperative words constructing adverb and verb structures. Well, although that’ what a *grin* is just big or wide smile, however, *grin* can have negative connotation which is an offensive smile, *cheerful* means happy, pleasant and bright attitude, so positive adverb describes the state with negative verb softly by overpowering it almost feels pleasantly, or extremely exaggerate – just as an actual look would, *neatly... claws* here neatly one can understand *tidy* and *cheerful* state, *claws* means a *sharp carved nail of wild animals* sometimes is used as *tool to catch something*, the author uses here the sharp tool as gently not with violently way, *gently jaws* – jaw is hard physical bone as a part of body by milder the appearance with adverb *gently*.

The author chose every word patterns in the rhyme sensitively, the reader has a little confusion if they have to think their cognitive meaning carefully. If we connect like examples with linguo – cognitive tendency, the semantic concept of words will be blossomed on part through the text under two different in combinations.

“ *I beg your pardon* ” said the Mouse, **frowning, but with very politely** ” this part is also taken from this story (p.45), “ *politely frowning* ” the author uses these two contradicting word patterns with gently, *frown* means an angry, unhappy, and disapprove attitude to someone or something offensively way but the author selected the positive adverb to mild the situation for readers’ cognitive concept.

“ *He was a cold man without feeling* ” (phrase from Robert Louise Stevenson, “ Dr Jerkyll and Mr Hyde” 2000. p.22) *cold* is low temperature of something not alive but *man* is opposite of it that is alive person here the speaker uses the Donative Linguistics Component accounts for the contradiction produced by the antonyms.

“ *I can remember another time , like a dream without shape or body: a world of eyes, sweet sad sounds and silent shadow. I woke up from hat long night, my eyes opened, and I saw the light of day again – here in this room full of thoughts and dreams.* ”

An analysis of *sweet sad* (phrase from Adgar Alan Poe, “ The black cat and other stories” 1991. p.19), amalgamated with adjective + adjective, identifying the emotion by modifier, the readers can be shown the head of this phrase is sounds, semantic marker is *sweet sad* which reversing emotion. That is, suppose the markers for sounds, sweet, and sad

sounds + (produce sound) vocal reason + types of feelings (emotion)

sweet

sad

so, the author uses the lexicon politely which the semantic marker connect the relation of grammar structures in the context as better response o the readers, in other words, this expression describes the concept of painful position without deep grief, *sweet sad* word structures indicate oxymoron which requires it like semantic interpretation to exaggerate the state into variety means in the contexts.

In conclusion, the way of analyzing the oxymoron concept in the literary texts show following results: finding proper approaches of method of oxymoron, the result of applied psychological concept in ambiguity words in readings, methods of using different ways of viewing semantic meaning, lexical form, syntax of word patterns. The sources of emotion (empathy) which may come from multiple readings that are possible from a given oxymoron that gives us an illusion of a multiple vision mimetic of the complexity of external and psychological reality of life as we actually experience it or mimetic of the different nuances of feelings of the writer or speaker of the oxymoron. Actually, variety resources of use oxymoron illustrates the richness of content under semantic meaning with grammar structures, especially on rhetorical uses which direct a reader to follow the conceptuality of oxymoron in the texts gently.

Susanne Langer says that all literature by the very nature of its language is able to overcome the linear expression of ideas in regular language give a semblance of the simultaneity ideas or feelings, the illusion of an integral picture of life.¹ Naturally, oxymoron show the action intentionally for effect while metaphor is direct similarity, so an oxymoron gives a sense of authentic style to readers accepting clear interpretation of expectation or gratification feelings.

¹ Ching,Marvel K. L., 1934. “ A Linguistic analysis of compact verbal paradox in literature. A semantic Interpretation of the Oxymoron”, p.258,(Langer, 1963. P.87)

In other words, the violations and deviations of literary language not chaotic but it is productive, meaningful, rewarding because of applying to these rules in literature by authors expressly.

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